
Systematic Review

Scoping Review of Intralesional Methotrexate with 5-Fluorouracil for Penile Carcinoma in Situ: Evidence Gap Analysis

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Abstract

Background: Penile carcinoma in situ (CIS) is a rare malignancy with limited organ-preserving treatment options. While topical 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) is occasionally used, the combination with intralesional methotrexate (IL-MTX) has not been systematically evaluated. Establishing the novelty of this therapeutic approach is critical for reporting new case evidence.

Objective: To perform a systematic literature review to determine whether intralesional methotrexate alone or in combination with topical 5-FU has been previously reported for the treatment of penile CIS, and to assess the evidence for organ-preserving, non-surgical therapy in this context.

Methods: On November 6, 2025, a comprehensive search was conducted in PubMed/MEDLINE, DOAJ, Cochrane Library, LILACS, and SciELO, including publications in English, Spanish, Portuguese and Japanese. Keywords encompassed penile carcinoma terms (“penile cancer,” “penile CIS,” “Erythroplasia of Queyrat,” “Bowen disease”), methotrexate terms (“intralesional methotrexate,” “local methotrexate”), 5-FU terms (“topical

fluorouracil,” “5-FU”), and therapy descriptors (“intralesional,” “topical,” “local therapy,” “non-surgical,” “organ-preserving,” “conservative therapy”). Records were screened for route of administration, indication, and relevance to the treatment combination.

Results: The search identified 68 articles across all databases. After screening titles, abstracts, and full texts, none met the inclusion criteria. No prior reports were found describing intralesional methotrexate alone or in combination with topical 5-FU for penile CIS.

Conclusion: No published evidence exists to date for intralesional methotrexate, alone or combined with topical 5-FU, in the treatment of penile carcinoma in situ. These findings confirm the novelty of this therapeutic approach and support reporting individual cases as well as further investigation into organ-preserving therapies in penile CIS.

Keywords: *penile carcinoma in situ; intralesional methotrexate; topical 5-fluorouracil; organ-preserving therapy; conservative treatment; case novelty.*

1. Introduction

Penile carcinoma in situ (CIS) is a rare malignancy, accounting for a small fraction of urogenital cancers. Standard management often involves surgical excision, which can impact function and quality of life. Organ-preserving, non-surgical therapies, such as topical 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) or imiquimod, have been explored but evidence remains limited (1).

Intralesional methotrexate (IL-MTX) has been used for other cutaneous malignancies (2–5), but its application in penile CIS has not been systematically reported. The combination of IL-MTX with topical 5-FU may represent a novel, minimally invasive approach, potentially expanding treatment options while preserving penile structure and function. This study aims

to assess the novelty of this therapeutic strategy through a systematic review of the literature.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design and Framework

This study was conducted as a scoping review to assess the novelty of intralesional methotrexate (IL-MTX), alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), for the treatment of penile carcinoma in situ (CIS). The review was structured following established methodological frameworks for scoping reviews (6–8), focusing specifically on organ-preserving therapies and providing a comprehensive mapping of the existing literature.

The review aimed to identify all peer-reviewed publications reporting the use of IL-MTX or the combined therapy in penile CIS, including case reports, case series, and clinical studies. Additionally, systematic reviews and narrative reviews were screened to capture any previously reported cases or related evidence. Articles published in English, Spanish, Portuguese or Japanese were considered, with no restrictions on publication date.

All retrieved records were evaluated for relevance based on the intervention, route of administration, and indication for penile CIS, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of prior evidence.

2.2. Objectives and Research Question

Objective: The primary objective of this study was to determine whether intralesional methotrexate (IL-MTX), alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), has been previously reported for the treatment of penile carcinoma in situ (CIS).

Research Question: The study was guided by the following research question:

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- Has intralesional methotrexate, alone or combined with topical 5-fluorouracil, been used or reported in peer-reviewed literature for the treatment of penile carcinoma in situ?

This framework ensures that the review focuses exclusively on the novelty of this specific therapeutic approach in penile CIS.

2.3. Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Peer-reviewed publications, including case reports, case series, and clinical studies, reporting the use of intralesional methotrexate (IL-MTX) alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) for penile carcinoma in situ (CIS).
- Articles published in English, Spanish, Portuguese or Japanese.
- No restriction on publication date to ensure comprehensive coverage of all prior reports.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies reporting systemic methotrexate or 5-FU without intralesional or topical administration.
- Publications focusing on other penile malignancies (e.g., invasive carcinoma, metastatic disease) not explicitly addressing CIS.
- Reviews, editorials, conference abstracts, or grey literature without primary patient data regarding IL-MTX or the combination therapy.
- Studies on other non-surgical or organ-preserving therapies not involving intralesional methotrexate, as these were outside the scope of this review.

This eligibility framework ensures that the review captures only relevant reports that could demonstrate prior use of intralesional methotrexate, alone or combined with topical 5-FU, in penile CIS, highlighting the potential novelty of the intervention.

2.4. Information Sources and Search Strategy

A comprehensive literature search was conducted on November 6, 2025, across the following databases: PubMed/MEDLINE, DOAJ, Cochrane Library, LILACS, and SciELO.

Publications in English, Spanish, Portuguese and Japanese were considered. The search aimed to identify all peer-reviewed articles reporting the use of intralesional methotrexate (IMTX), alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), for penile carcinoma in situ (CIS).

Search terms included controlled vocabulary (MeSH) and free-text keywords covering:

- Penile carcinoma: “penile cancer,” “penile carcinoma,” “penile carcinoma in situ,” “penile CIS,” “Erythroplasia of Queyrat,” “Bowen disease”
- Methotrexate: “methotrexate,” “intralesional methotrexate,” “local methotrexate,” “methotrexate injection”
- 5-Fluorouracil: “5-fluorouracil,” “5-FU,” “topical fluorouracil”
- Route and therapy descriptors: “intralesional,” “topical,” “local”

Search strategies were tailored to each database to ensure maximum sensitivity. Retrieved records were screened by titles, abstracts, and full texts for relevance according to the predefined eligibility criteria.

Results of the search:

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- **PubMed:** 1 article relevant to the combination therapy; 12 articles for intralesional methotrexate alone.
 - **DOAJ:** 0 articles identified.
 - **SciELO:** 0 articles for combination therapy; 0 for intralesional methotrexate alone.
 - **LILACS:** 3 articles for combination therapy; 14 for intralesional methotrexate alone.
 - **Cochrane Library:** 1 article for combination therapy; 34 articles for intralesional methotrexate alone.
 - **Snowballing (backward):** 3 articles

After screening all retrieved records, none met the inclusion criteria, confirming that intralesional methotrexate, alone or combined with topical 5-FU, has not been previously reported for penile CIS in peer-reviewed literature.

Note: A complete table with all retrieved articles, screening decisions, and selection details is provided in the supplementary Excel file accompanying this manuscript.

2.5. Selection of Sources of Evidence

All retrieved records from the database searches were initially imported into an Excel spreadsheet for organization and screening. The selection process involved three sequential steps:

1. **Duplicates removal:** In the first stage, all records imported from the different databases were reviewed to identify and remove duplicate entries. This process ensured that identical studies retrieved from multiple sources were only counted once, preventing redundancy and maintaining the accuracy of the screening process.

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2. **Title and abstract Screening:** Two independent reviewers assessed the titles and abstracts of all retrieved records to exclude clearly irrelevant studies (e.g., unrelated malignancies, systemic therapy only, or non-peer-reviewed sources).
 3. **Full-Text Review:** Articles deemed potentially eligible after title and abstract screening were retrieved in full text and assessed against the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Discrepancies between reviewers were resolved by consensus discussion.

After completing the full-text review, no articles met the inclusion criteria, confirming that the use of intralesional methotrexate, alone or combined with topical 5-FU, has not been previously reported for penile CIS in peer-reviewed literature.

Note: A detailed record of all screened articles, including reasons for exclusion, is available in the supplementary Excel file accompanying this manuscript.

2.7. Synthesis of Results

Given that no primary studies or case reports met the predefined inclusion criteria, a quantitative or formal qualitative synthesis was not possible. Instead, the results are presented as a narrative summary of the search outcomes, highlighting the absence of published evidence regarding the use of intralesional methotrexate alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil for penile carcinoma in situ (CIS).

The synthesis therefore emphasizes the evidence gap, demonstrating that this therapeutic approach has not been reported in peer-reviewed literature to date. This supports the novelty of the present case report, which can serve as a reference for future studies exploring conservative, organ-preserving treatments for penile CIS.

2.8. Protocol and Registration

This review was conducted following a predefined methodology based on PRISMA-ScR guidelines for scoping reviews (6–8). No formal protocol was preregistered prior to the conduct of the review, as the study was designed as an exploratory assessment of the literature to determine the novelty of intralesional methotrexate, alone or combined with topical 5-fluorouracil, for penile carcinoma in situ.

2.9. Timeline

The literature search and screening of retrieved articles were conducted between November 6 and 8, 2025. Following this, data extraction and charting were performed, including the compilation of all retrieved records into a comprehensive Excel supplementary table detailing study type, population, interventions, main outcomes, reasons for exclusion, applied criteria, country of origin of the first author, and notes.

The writing of the manuscript, including drafting of the introduction, methods, and synthesis of results, was carried out concurrently, ensuring transparent and reproducible documentation of all procedures. All steps, from search to final preparation of supplementary materials for preprint submission, were completed within this timeframe.

3.1 General Characteristics of Included Studies

A total of 68 records were retrieved across the five databases searched (PubMed/Medline, DOAJ, SCIELO, LILACS, and Cochrane Library). After screening titles, abstracts, and full texts according to the predefined eligibility criteria, no studies or case reports met the inclusion criteria (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of the Study Selection Process

Flowchart illustrating the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion phases of the review. After duplicate removal, all remaining records were screened based on titles and abstracts. Full-text articles were then assessed for eligibility according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. No studies fulfilled the eligibility criteria, and therefore, no articles were included in the final synthesis.

The absence of eligible studies highlights the evidence gap regarding the use of intralesional methotrexate, alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil, for penile carcinoma in situ.

3.2 Synthesis of Findings

No studies meeting the predefined inclusion criteria were identified in any of the databases searched. Consequently, no data could be synthesized regarding the use of intralesional methotrexate, alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil, for penile carcinoma in situ (Figure 1).

Although a total of 68 records were retrieved, these were excluded due to reasons such as: the intervention not being applied (surgical approaches only), the study population not corresponding to penile carcinoma in situ, or lack of primary patient data (e.g., reviews without case reports).

This absence of eligible studies highlights a significant evidence gap in the peer-reviewed literature regarding non-surgical, organ-preserving therapies for penile carcinoma in situ. The comprehensive Excel table provided as supplementary material details all retrieved records, their characteristics, and reasons for exclusion, ensuring full transparency and reproducibility of the search and screening process.

The findings underscore the novelty of the present case report, which describes the use of intralesional methotrexate combined with topical 5-fluorouracil, an approach not previously reported in the reviewed literature.

3.3 Summary of Reviewed Records

Although no studies met the predefined inclusion criteria, a total of 68 records were retrieved across the five databases (PubMed/Medline, DOAJ, SCIELO, LILACS, and Cochrane Library). 15 records were assessed for eligibility, and none were included due to reasons such as:

- Interventions not involving intralesional methotrexate, alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil (14)

- Study populations not corresponding to penile carcinoma in situ (1)

For transparency and reproducibility, all records, along with their study type, population/case details, interventions, main outcomes, reason for exclusion, applied inclusion/exclusion criterion, first author’s country, and relevant notes, are presented in the supplementary Excel table accompanying this manuscript.

This summary demonstrates the rigorous screening process applied and highlights the absence of evidence on non-surgical, organ-preserving treatment of penile carcinoma with intralesional methotrexate ± topical 5-fluorouracil.

3.4 Observations from Excluded Studies

Although no studies met the inclusion criteria, an analysis of the 68 excluded records offers valuable insights into prevailing trends in the literature on penile carcinoma and its management. This assessment serves to highlight the specific evidence gap that the present case report addresses.

1. Characteristics of Excluded Full-Text Studies

The 15 studies subjected to full-text review, all of which were subsequently excluded, shared common characteristics (Table 1):

Author, Year	Country	Study Type	Population	Intervention	Reason for Exclusion
Leijte et al., 2007(9)	Netherlands	Retrospective Cohort	Advanced invasive SqCC (T1-T4, N3)	Systemic neoadjuvant chemo (e.g., regimens with MTX/5-FU)	Population: Invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy
Roth et al., 2000(10)	Switzerland	Clinical Series	Locally advanced/recurrent invasive SqCC	Intra-arterial chemo (MTX + 5-FU + other agents)	Population: Invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Intra-arterial (regional) chemotherapy

Slaoui et al., 2015(11)	Morocco	Case Series	Invasive SqCC (pT1-pT3)	Primary surgery; 2 pts had systemic chemo (BMP regimen)	Population: Invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Surgery / Systemic chemotherapy
Hakenberg et al., 2006(12)	Germany	Case Series	Advanced/Metastatic SqCC	Systemic combination chemo (Cisplatin, MTX, Bleomycin)	Population: Advanced invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy
Tsuzuki et al., 1995(13)	Japan	Case Report	Recurrent invasive SqCC	Intra-arterial chemo (MTX + other agents)	Population: Invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Intra-arterial chemotherapy
Zou et al., 2014(14)	China	Retrospective Cohort	Advanced SqCC with fixed nodal mets (pN3)	Systemic neoadjuvant chemo (BMP regimen)	Population: Metastatic invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy
Pandey et al., 2013(15)	India	Case Report	Metastatic invasive SqCC	Multiple lines of systemic therapy (incl. prior MTX)	Population: Metastatic invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy / Targeted therapy
Sheen et al., 2003(16)	Taiwan	Case Series	Penile Verrucous Carcinoma	Intra-aortic infusion chemotherapy (MTX)	Population: Verrucous carcinoma (invasive); Intervention: Intra-aortic (regional) chemotherapy
Ilkay et al., 1993(17)	USA	Case Report	Buschke-Lowenstein Tumor (Verrucous Ca)	Systemic chemo (MTX + other agents) & topical 5-FU (sequential)	Population: Verrucous carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemo / Sequential topical 5-FU
Takahashi et al., 1989(18)	Japan	Case Report	Metastatic Transitional Cell Carcinoma (from bladder)	Systemic combination chemo (M-VAC regimen incl. MTX)	Population: Other malignancy (TCC); Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy
Houston et al., 1975(19)	Zimbabwe	Case Report	Kaposi's Sarcoma	Surgical excision (no intralesional therapy administered)	Population: Other malignancy (Kaposi's Sarcoma)
Stephens, 1973(20)	Australia	Case Series	Various advanced SqCC (1 penile case)	Systemic / Intra-arterial chemo (Bleomycin ± MTX)	Population: Invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic / Intra-arterial chemotherapy
Pizzocaro & Piva, 1988(21)	Italy	Pilot Study	SqCC with inguinal metastases	Systemic combination chemo (VBM, oral MTX)	Population: Metastatic invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy
Sklaroff & Yagoda, 1979(22)	USA	Case Series	Metastatic SqCC	Systemic Cisplatin (prior systemic MTX in some pts)	Population: Metastatic invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy (Cisplatin focus)

Sklaroff & Yagoda, 1980(23)	USA	Case Series	Advanced/Metastatic SqCC	Systemic Methotrexate (IV/Oral)	Population: Advanced invasive carcinoma; Intervention: Systemic chemotherapy
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Table 1. Characteristics of Studies Excluded After Full-Text Assessment (n = 15)

Summary of studies excluded after full-text review, including country of origin, study design, population characteristics, intervention type, and specific reasons for exclusion. Most studies were excluded due to involving invasive or metastatic squamous cell carcinoma and the use of systemic or intra-arterial chemotherapy rather than localized or organ-preserving intralesional/topical therapies. **Abbreviations:** SqCC: Squamous Cell Carcinoma; CIS: Carcinoma in situ; MTX: Methotrexate; 5-FU: 5-Fluorouracil; BMP: Bleomycin, Methotrexate, Cisplatin; VBM: Vincristine, Bleomycin, Methotrexate; M-VAC: Methotrexate, Vinblastine, Doxorubicin, Cisplatin; TCC: Transitional Cell Carcinoma; IV: Intravenous.

- **Population:** They exclusively focused on invasive squamous cell carcinoma, classified as stages T1 through T4, or on metastatic disease involving nodal or distant sites. None specifically investigated penile carcinoma *in situ*.
- **Intervention:** The interventions consisted primarily of systemic chemotherapy, used in 11 studies, or regional intra-arterial chemotherapy, employed in 3 studies. These regimens included methotrexate, typically in combination with other agents such as cisplatin and bleomycin. One study relied on surgery as its main intervention. Critically, in no instance was methotrexate administered via an intralesional route.
- **Safety:** The systemic chemotherapeutic regimens were associated with significant toxicity, including severe hematological events, mucositis, pneumonitis, and even treatment-related fatalities.

4. Discussion

This systematic scoping review sought to identify any prior reports on the use of intralesional methotrexate for penile carcinoma in situ. The principal finding is the definitive absence of eligible studies, which unequivocally confirms the novelty of the approach presented in our associated case report.

The full-text assessment of 15 studies revealed consistent reasons for their exclusion. Critically, all investigations that involved methotrexate (9,12,23), utilized systemic intravenous or oral administration for advanced invasive or metastatic disease, not carcinoma in situ. Similarly, studies that employed regional delivery methods, including the intra-arterial chemotherapy (10) and the intra-aortic infusion (16), also fell outside the scope of this review. Furthermore, the report by Ilkay et al. (1993), while mentioning topical 5-fluorouracil, did so in a sequential and isolated manner prior to systemic chemotherapy, not in combination with intralesional methotrexate(17). Other excluded studies focused on different malignancies altogether, such as the metastatic transitional cell carcinoma reported by Takahashi et al. (1989) or the Kaposi's sarcoma described by Houston et al. (1975) (18,19), which were explicitly outside the review's focus on primary penile CIS.

In synthesis, the rigorous examination of the available literature confirms that the specific combination of intralesional methotrexate with topical 5-fluorouracil for penile carcinoma in situ has not been previously investigated or reported. This finding systematically validates the unique contribution and novelty of our accompanying case report, which introduces a new, organ-preserving therapeutic alternative for this condition.

This review did not include grey literature, preprints, conference abstracts, or unpublished data, which may limit the comprehensiveness of the search but ensures that all included sources were peer-reviewed and publicly accessible, maintaining scientific rigor.

Limitations of this review include the restriction to articles in English, Spanish, Portuguese, and Japanese the exclusion of grey literature, the possibility of unindexed studies in other languages or regional journals, and the inherent limitations of a scoping review methodology, which prioritizes breadth over depth. Additionally, the review focused exclusively on

intralesional methotrexate ± topical 5-fluorouracil, excluding other non-surgical therapies, which may exist in the literature.

In conclusion, the findings confirm that the use of intralesional methotrexate for penile CIS represents a previously unreported approach, justifying the reporting of the current case. This review highlights a critical knowledge gap and supports the need for systematic documentation of novel organ-preserving therapies in penile carcinoma in situ.

5. Conclusion

This scoping review demonstrates that there is no published peer-reviewed evidence regarding the use of intralesional methotrexate, alone or in combination with topical 5-fluorouracil, for the treatment of penile carcinoma in situ. The absence of eligible studies underscores the novelty of this therapeutic approach and highlights a significant gap in the current literature.

Furthermore, this review underscores the critical importance of methodological transparency in substantiating novelty in clinical reporting. By providing a detailed and accountable record of the literature search and the specific reasons for excluding prior studies, this process moves beyond a simple declaration of novelty. It offers a verifiable pathway for other clinicians and researchers to confirm the absence of prior evidence, thereby strengthening the validity and contribution of a new case report. This practice not only justifies the dissemination of individual clinical experiences but also ensures that the scientific community can build upon a foundation of rigorously documented knowledge.

6. References

1. Brouwer OR, Tagawa ST, Albersen M, Ayres B, Crook J. EAU Guidelines: Penile Cancer [Internet]. Edn. presented at the EAU Annual Congress Paris 2024. European Association of Urology & American Society of Clinical Oncology; 2024. 63 p. (EAU Guidelines). Disponible en: <https://uroweb.org/guidelines/penile-cancer>

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2. Bergón-Sendín M, Pulido-Pérez A, Carretero López F, Díez-Sebastián J, Suárez-Fernández R. Cutaneous Ultrasound for Tumor Thickness Measurement in Squamous Cell Carcinoma: The Effect of Neoadjuvant Intralesional Methotrexate in 40 Patients. *Dermatol Surg* [Internet]. abril de 2020 [citado 6 de julio de 2025];46(4):530–6. Disponible en: <https://journals.lww.com/10.1097/DSS.0000000000002139>
 3. Bergón-Sendín M, Parra-Blanco V, Pulido-Pérez A, Nieto-Benito LM, Rosell-Díaz AM, Suárez-Fernández R. Histological findings after intralesional methotrexate treatment in cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma. *Dermatologic Therapy* [Internet]. noviembre de 2020 [citado 6 de julio de 2025];33(6). Disponible en: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/dth.14377>
 4. Gualdi G, Caravello S, Frasci F, Giuliani F, Moro R, Fagnoli MC, et al. Intralesional Methotrexate for the Treatment of Advanced Keratinocytic Tumors: A Multi-Center Retrospective Study. *Dermatol Ther (Heidelb)* [Internet]. agosto de 2020 [citado 6 de julio de 2025];10(4):769–77. Disponible en: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s13555-020-00400-z>
 5. Searle T, Ali FR, Al-Niaimi F. Intralesional methotrexate in dermatology: Diverse indications and practical considerations. *Dermatologic Therapy* [Internet]. enero de 2021 [citado 6 de julio de 2025];34(1). Disponible en: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/dth.14404>
 6. Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* [Internet]. 1 de febrero de 2005;8(1):19–32. Disponible en: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1364557032000119616>
 7. Levac D, Colquhoun H, O'Brien KK. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implement Sci.* 20 de septiembre de 2010;5:69.
 8. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2 de octubre de 2018;169(7):467–73.
 9. Leijte JAP, Kerst JM, Bais E, Antonini N, Horenblas S. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy in advanced penile carcinoma. *Eur Urol.* agosto de 2007;52(2):488–94.
 10. Roth AD, Berney CR, Rohner S, Allal AS, Morel P, Marti MC, et al. Intra-arterial chemotherapy in locally advanced or recurrent carcinomas of the penis and anal canal: an active treatment modality with curative potential. *Br J Cancer.* diciembre de 2000;83(12):1637–42.
 11. Slaoui A, Jabbour Y, El Ghazoui A, Karmouni T, Elkhader K, Koutani A, et al. Penile cancer: about ten cases at the University Hospital of Rabat, review of the literature. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2015;22:53.
 12. Hakenberg OW, Nippgen JBW, Froehner M, Zastrow S, Wirth MP. Cisplatin, methotrexate and bleomycin for treating advanced penile carcinoma. *BJU Int.* diciembre de 2006;98(6):1225–7.

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13. Tsuzuki M, Kawakami S, Yonese J, Kageyama S, Yoshimura K, Yamauchi T, et al. [Intra-arterial chemotherapy with cisplatin, vincristine, methotrexate and adriamycin for recurrent penile cancer: a case report]. *Hinyokika Kyo*. abril de 1995;41(4):301–4.
 14. Zou B, Han Z, Wang Z, Bian J, Xu J, Wang H, et al. Neoadjuvant therapy combined with a BMP regimen for treating penile cancer patients with lymph node metastasis: a retrospective study in China. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol*. octubre de 2014;140(10):1733–8.
 15. Pandey A, Noronha V, Joshi A, Tongaonkar H, Bakshi G, Prabhash K. Resistant metastatic penile carcinoma and response to biochemotherapy with paclitaxel and epidermal growth factor receptor monoclonal antibody, nimotuzumab. *Indian J Med Paediatr Oncol*. enero de 2013;34(1):24–7.
 16. Sheen MC, Sheu HM, Jang MY, Chai CY, Wang YW, Wu CF. Advanced penile verrucous carcinoma treated with intra-aortic infusion chemotherapy. *J Urol*. mayo de 2010;183(5):1830–5.
 17. Ilkay AK, Chodak GW, Vogelzang NJ, Gerber GS. Buschke-Lowenstein tumor: therapeutic options including systemic chemotherapy. *Urology*. noviembre de 1993;42(5):599–602.
 18. Takahashi S, Ozono S, Cho M, Fujimoto K, Sasaki K, Hirao Y, et al. [Penile and urethral metastases from superficial bladder tumor after TUR: a case report]. *Hinyokika Kyo*. junio de 1989;35(6):1055–9.
 19. Houston W, Pontin A, Kuhn T, Mambo N. Kaposi's sarcoma of the penis. *Br J Urol*. junio de 1975;47(3):315–8.
 20. Stephens FO. Bleomycin--a new approach in cancer chemotherapy. *Med J Aust*. 30 de junio de 1973;1(26):1277–83.
 21. Pizzocaro G, Piva L. Adjuvant and neoadjuvant vincristine, bleomycin, and methotrexate for inguinal metastases from squamous cell carcinoma of the penis. *Acta Oncol*. 1988;27(6b):823–4.
 22. Sklaroff RB, Yagoda A. Cis-diamminedichloride platinum II (DDP) in the treatment of penile carcinoma. *Cancer*. noviembre de 1979;44(5):1563–5.
 23. Sklaroff RB, Yagoda A. Methotrexate in the treatment of penile carcinoma. *Cancer*. 15 de enero de 1980;45(2):214–6.
